

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

THE PROCESS OF GLOBALIZATION IN THE FOCUS OF CIVIL SOCIETY

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ABSTRACT

Civil society and globalization interact in a complex way. Globalization, which consists of increasing economic, social and cultural interaction between countries, can have both positive and negative consequences for civil society. On the one hand, globalization can contribute to the development of civil society by spreading democratic values, increasing the availability of information, and increasing opportunities for International Cooperation and exchange of ideas. On the other hand, globalization can also increase the impact of large corporations on society, reduce cultural diversity, and deepen inequality between nations. Therefore, it is important that civil society be active in interacting with the processes of globalization.

Keywords: globalization, civil society, democracy, state, personality, politics, rule of law, freedom, public relations.

The relevance of the study is determined by the issue of the formation and development of civil society in Ukraine, which is now gaining scientific, theoretical and socio-practical significance. The activation of civil society and the formation of a state governed by the rule of law is a necessity for the formation of statehood. The importance of civil society in systemic transformations contributes to increasing scientific and practical interest in the question of correlation between the idea, concept, and concept of civil society. The study of the peculiarities of interaction between state institutions and civil society is one of the most modern areas of socio-political research, the object of which is the state, civil society, as well as models and relevant mechanisms and procedures for their interaction.

In transitive societies, such as Ukraine, the processes of integration into established advanced European economic, social and cultural systems represent a set of steps providing for the adaptation of local socio-cultural practices to regional and globalized socio-political trends. At the same time, it is assumed that economic specialization, socio-cultural and national priorities should not they may be lost, but on the contrary, a comprehensive effectiveness effect can be achieved.

In the course of European integration, much depends not only on from the generation of values within the framework of national cultural projects, but also from the reception of innovative trends in the political, legal, economic and cultural spheres of life. Horizontal, interstate transfer of knowledge and practices provides accelerated socio-cultural dynamics.

The relevance of the study of the features of the formation of modern civil society is determined by the need to identify the conditions for optimizing democratic transformations and overcome the anthropological crisis of man-made civilization. Globalization as a context of sociocultural transformations is considered as a multilevel, multidimensional object. The main

problem seems to be as a search for new civic forms of democratization and social practices in a globalizing world.

In the works on civil society, the term "global civil society" is increasingly found. However, nowhere is a clear definition of this term given, which, obviously, simply does not exist, just as there is no generally accepted definition of "civil society" itself.

At the same time, in these studies, the authors argue that the formation of a global civil society is associated with the processes of globalization. But how? Is it about the part of society that protests against globalization or about the process of forming some kind of supranational civil society associations that advocate globalization, or maybe it's something else?

The prospects of classical civil society, its possible vectors of transformation and development under the influence of globalization are analyzed in the works of S. Giner [8], K. Galbraith [7], R. Dalton, M. Kuhler [4] and others.

The relationship between the state and civil society, as well as the issue of weakening the role of the state under the influence of globalization and the consequences of this process for civil society are considered in the studies of E. Gouldner [9], R. Cox [3], K. Schmitt [11] and others.

In Ukraine, this discussion received a new incentive in connection with the problems of strengthening Ukrainian statehood and increasing the role of Legal Regulation, forming a new style of relations between the government and society. Such researchers as V. Bebik, V. Bortnikov, L. Kudryachenko [2], I. Dinnik [6], I. Zhidan, S. Kiselyov, O. Kiseleva, S. Ryabov [12], S. Sidorenko [10] in their works pay considerable attention to the formation and development of civil society.

The concept of "civil society" is considered by Ukrainian political science in several aspects, for example, as a sphere of freedom of individuals, free from forced restriction by the state, or as a public organization that protects human rights. Highlighting previously unsolved parts of a common problem. Now there is a need to analyze from the point of view of modern approaches and knowledge accumulated by Socio-Political Sciences, the structure and dynamics of the development of modern civil society and get the opportunity to find out how universal this concept is and what global restrictions secretly affect the actions of social actors that directly affect civil society and change it in the context of globalization.

The most common is the perception of civil society through the analysis of public organizations and movements. Civil society is a certain set of Public Communications and social relations, institutions and values, the main subjects of which are: citizens and civil (non-political and non-governmental) organizations with civil rights: associations, associations, social movements and public institutions.

Civil society is a society consisting of informal structures in the form of various political parties, organizations, movements, committees, associations, assemblies, societies, etc. that operate in the legal and regulatory field and have a significant impact on society.

All these definitions do not contradict each other, but indicate that civil society is a complex, multifactorial and multifactorial phenomenon.

Civil society is defined as follows. First, civil society consists of social groups that people voluntarily join under a social contract. Secondly, these social groups operate in the public sphere and meet the following requirements: their activities should be open to some form of external control that can determine the degree of compliance with the current legislation; the results of their activities should be available for broad discussion and analysis. In other words, society is transparent and accountable to society.

Third, the characteristics of social groups belonging to this "transparent and accountable society" are: tolerance to other similar groups, willingness to cooperate or compete with them according to established rules; horizontal structures of interaction; forms of democratic government. This makes it possible to exclude secret organizations, anti-democratic, intolerant hierarchical structures, and organizations that are prosecuted by law. The fourth feature that needs to be emphasized in an effective description of civil society is its legal status in relation to the state (government). A well-developed "classical" civil society is possible only if it is transparent and operates within the social space protected by law.

The conceptual development of the concept of civil society has two directions: 1) identification of civil society with the state, the rights and freedoms of the individual are guaranteed legally and politically; 2) its allocation as a sphere of non-state Public Relations. In the second direction, there are two views on the relationship between "politics" and "society" in the institutional system of civil society. The first explains civil society as a non-political, non-governmental sphere of

interpersonal relations. Representatives of the second approach recognize that civil society is a political phenomenon.

Civil society as a system of public relations and institutions has the following properties: it is non-state in nature, guarantees a person the exercise of his rights, expresses various interests of Free members of society.

The functions of civil society include: limiting the power of officials, including monitoring and combating the crime of those in power; monitoring the observance of human rights and strengthening the rule of law and order; monitoring elections, ensuring the highest level of democracy and increasing confidence in democratic processes; legal education, explaining rights and obligations, creating a common atmosphere of understanding and civic participation in the life of the country, the participation of various social groups and movements in the political process, increasing their activity in protecting public interests; development of alternative ways to improve the level of public welfare; ensuring transparency and pluralism by informing the public about the consistency in the implementation of economic and political reforms.

The terms "democracy", "rule of law" and "economic freedom" are also used in the context of general concepts with the term "civil society". Therefore, most researchers believe that such a social system is established with the help of civil society, creating the most favorable conditions for the development of the human personality and social organization.

The formation of civil society is directly related to the formation of the rule of law, which is the result of the development and improvement of civil society.

Thus, the evolution of social institutions can often be described in the form of a linear scheme "society – state – civil society – rule of law". This program clearly shows that the formation of the rule of law is a rather long process in the history of mankind. The process of globalization has led to fundamental qualitative changes in all spheres of public life – economic, political, social, spiritual, which requires a deep socio-philosophical understanding and analysis of modern ideas about the transformation of world society.

Recently, the emergence of a "global", "global" or "transnational civil society" has been widely discussed, which is associated with the interrelated processes of strengthening the role of international organizations, globalization and the entry of non-state actors. The world stage acts as an autonomous participant in the global political process.

In the context of globalization, the state as the main institutional component loses some of its traditional functions, erodes as an important part of the political, economic and social space with national borders. The traditional dichotomy between the state and civil society has ceased to be national.

Transnational enterprises, which are becoming a model of this world, are breaking out from under the previous forms of state control, and civil society in these conditions is being replaced by a decentralized world community. Some Western scientists have started talking about the formation of a post-civil society.

The growing ideological and value conflict between the consciousness of transnational actors and the national consciousness of individual citizens of a particular country is another threat to national democratic institutions from globalization.

Today, the individual is being transformed into a global consumer. The individual turns from an active subject to a passive participant in socio-political life, closing in on the private sphere. V. Bebik notes that "global civil society is a system of public institutions and relations that do not depend on the structures of the global state (supranational, interstate and state-National), which are just being formed, and at the same time they should create conditions for self-realization of all mankind, individual nations, social groups and individuals" [1; p. 141].

As O. Demyanenko notes, "civil society today is defined by a diverse and broad ecosystem of individuals and organizations. Information and communication technologies open up a space of power, influence and connections with new configurations of actors, which has led to a significant increase in the activity of online civil society and the creation of networks created beyond geographical, social and physical differences. These networks allow more people to unite and jointly respond to social challenges" [5; p. 138].

Thus, the transition to civil society is a rather complex and lengthy civilized process. Globalization is not limited to institutional changes. It significantly changes the foundations of previous forms of political culture and national mentality. As a result of global processes, global interdependence, the interweaving of global and local is growing. This creates difficult conditions for the existence and development of civil society.

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